

D6.4: Methodology to help public research funding organisations reconcile the views and interests of scientists and citizens

[WP6 – Generalizing project methods, and exploitation measures]

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Abstract

This report presents the SIENNA methodology for public research funding organisations (PRFOs) to identify and address societal concerns in research related to new and emerging technologies. Taking in account PRFOs’ role in the research process and the needs of researchers to have clarity, flexibility, and support, this methodology provides a framework for reconciling researchers’ needs with the concerns of the general public. For the purpose of this methodology, we define ‘societal concerns’ as issues (1) identified by the general public, (2) related to negative impacts or harms, (3) that result – directly or indirectly – from research activities and outputs involving new and emerging technologies. The methodology is divided into three steps: (1) identify and define relevant societal concerns, (2) understand how research creates impact, and (3) address societal concerns and mitigate harm. Each step includes recommendations for PRFOs, as well as specific ideas to implement the recommendation. These recommendations are formulated to provide PRFOs with a practical method and range of tools that can be adapted and implemented, in part or in whole, to address societal concerns related to research involving new and emerging technologies. The methodology was developed with input from previous SIENNA work, including public opinion surveys and citizen panels, and consultation with experts from PRFOs in workshops, individual interviews, and written feedback.

Document history

Version	Date	Description	Reason for change	Distribution
V0.1	October 2020	Outline	Develop outline	Internal
V0.2	January 2021	Draft methodology	Review	Internal and External
V1.0	1 February 2021	Final draft	Quality assurance review	Internal
V2.0	28 February 2021	Final report	-	-
V3.0	2 March 2021	Final report	Minor edit in Executive Summary and added additional reviewer	-
V4.0	6 July 2021	Final report	Check following final review	

Information in this report that may influence other SIENNA tasks

Linked task	Points of relevance
Task 6.4: Obtain buy-in for SIENNA proposals from EU and international institutions	The methodology will be shared with PRFOs and other stakeholders, and published. An open webinar will also be organised on 5 March 2021.
T6.6: Formulate a sustainability plan	The methodology will be included in the sustainability plan (D6.5).

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Executive summary

This report presents the SIENNA methodology for public research funding organisations (PRFOs) to identify and address societal concerns in research related to new and emerging technologies. Both PRFOs and researchers have an obligation to the public to ensure that research related to new and emerging technologies has a positive impact on society, which means that societal concerns must be identified and addressed in ways that avoid and mitigate harm. Taking in account PRFOs' role in the research process and the needs of researchers to have clarity, flexibility, and support, this methodology provides a framework for reconciling researchers' needs with the concerns of the general public. The methodology is tailored to PRFOs and can be adapted for use by any organisation involved in funding research activities in new and emerging technologies.

For the purpose of this methodology, we define 'societal concerns' as issues (1) identified by the general public, (2) related to negative impacts or harms, (3) that result – directly or indirectly – from research activities and outputs involving emerging technologies. While there is no exhaustive list of societal concerns, as types and categories of societal concerns will evolve and change over time as negative impacts emerge and are better understood, a list of societal concerns identified in the SIENNA project are presented in the Annex as a baseline.

The methodology is divided into three steps: (1) identify and define relevant societal concerns, (2) understand how research creates impact, and (3) address societal concerns and mitigate harm. Each step includes recommendations for PRFOs, as well as specific ideas to implement the recommendation. These recommendations are formulated to provide PRFOs with a practical method and range of tools that can be adapted and implemented, in part or in whole, to address societal concerns related to research involving new and emerging technologies.

Development of this methodology draws on existing frameworks and risk assessment methodologies related to addressing societal concerns, such Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI); Ethical, legal and social implications/aspects (ELSI/ELSA) approach; Broader Impact criteria; and social, ethical, environmental, and socio-economic impact assessments. However, this methodology is intended to more comprehensively capture broader societal concerns about impacts of new and emerging technologies – including ethical, human rights, and socio-economic impacts – and specifically provides guidance to PRFOs.

The methodology was developed through desk research and consultation with experts from PRFOs, which was provided during two online workshops with representatives from PRFOs in December 2020, individual interviews, and written feedback on a draft of the methodology.

List of acronyms/abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
PRFO	Public research funding organisation
RRI	Responsible research and innovation
T	Task
WP	Work package

Table 1: List of acronyms/abbreviations

Glossary of terms

Term	Explanation
public research funding organisation	Government body providing funding for research.
Societal concerns	Issues (1) identified by the general public, (2) related to negative impacts or harms, that (3) result – directly or indirectly – from research outputs involving emerging technologies.
Research outputs	Knowledge (general and applied), artifacts (e.g. products, services, and platforms), and data that are created by or result from research activities.

Table 2: Glossary of terms

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

This document addresses SIENNA DoA Task 6.5 description: “The goal of Task 6.5 is to develop a general methodology that could be used by public research funding organisations (testing it in the context of genomics, human enhancement and human-machine interaction) to help reconcile the needs of scientific researchers (e.g., access to biological materials for research) and the legitimate concerns of citizens (e.g., abuse of sensitive data). First, we will consider existing methods of addressing societal concern about research activities (such as the European Commission’s H2020 Societal Impact Assessment, ASSERT Toolkit for Societal Impact Assessment. Then, we will develop a new general methodology, using as starting point the ‘DISCOVER-DEFINE- ENGAGE-ADDRESS’ elements which underlie various risk assessment and impact assessment methodologies. **The methodology will be evaluated and refined in discussion with representatives from research-funding organisations as well as experts in mediation at a project workshop.** We will also incorporate the results from stakeholder engagement in WPs 2, 3 and 4 as input for this task in order further to test and refine the methodology. The innovation in the methodology will be its potential to be adapted for use by any organisation that wishes to accommodate the concerns of the general public in making decisions about research activities. The results of this task will be presented in a report circulated to public research-funding organisations at the EU level and national level (in the countries represented in the project, and more widely as feasible). Finally, we will organise an open invitation webinar for interested parties in order to promote the uptake of the methodology.”

1.2 Objectives

The objective of this task is to develop a methodology to help public research funding organisations (PRFOs) reconcile the views and interests of scientists and citizens [D6.4]. The methodology is tailored for PRFOs, however the generalised approach could be adapted for use by any organisation involved in funding research activities related to new and emerging technologies.

1.3 Structure of the report

Section 1 provides an introduction to this report. Section 2 discusses the methodology for developing this report, including how related SIENNA results were incorporated. Section 3 discusses researchers’ needs and societal concerns. Section 4 presents the three-step SIENNA methodology for addressing societal concerns, with recommendations for each step and ideas about how to implement each recommendation.

The Annex contains a list of societal concerns identified in the SIENNA project related to the three SIENNA research areas: genomics, human enhancement, and AI and robotics.

1.4 Scope and limitations

The scope of this task is limited to publicly funded research (as opposed to privately funded research) related to new and emerging technologies.

The primary objective of the methodology is to identify and address societal concerns. We developed and use the term ‘societal concerns’ in place of “legitimate concerns of citizens” to reflect the collective concerns of the public and to be inclusive of non-citizens. Additionally, we broadened our approach in the methodology from ‘reconcile’ to ‘identify and address’ societal concerns, as awareness and identification of societal concerns is a critical first step to balancing needs and concerns. Taking into account PRFOs’ role in the research process and the needs of researchers to have clarity, flexibility, and support, we have also proposed a range of specific ways to address and mitigate harms, designed to help PRFOs reconcile researchers’ needs and the public’s concerns.

2. Methodology

The methodology to address and identify societal concerns (PRFO methodology) was developed through desk research and consultation with experts from PRFOs.

Desk research was performed as background and context to developing the PRFO methodology. We looked at current funding policies and procedures at PRFOs in Europe, including the European Commission’s Horizon 2020 funding programme and PRFOs in Austria, Ireland, Latvia, Norway, Poland, Sweden, and the United Kingdom, as well as in the United States. Additionally, we looked at existing frameworks and risks assessment methodologies related to addressing societal concerns, including: Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)¹; Ethical, legal and social implications/aspects (ELSI/ELSA) approach²; and Broader Impact criteria³. For impact assessments, we looked at work in the EU-funded SATORI project to develop a CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA) on ethics assessment of research and innovation,⁴ the ASSERT Toolkit for Societal Impact Assessment,⁵ and parallel work in the SIENNA project on socio-economic impact assessments in SIENNA Task 6.1 (Adapting and exploiting methods developed in this project for ethical analysis in other domains).⁶

¹ European Commission, “Responsible Research and Innovation”. Accessed February 2021.

<https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/responsible-research-innovation>

² National Human Genome Research Institute, “Ethical, Legal and Social Implications Research Program”.

Accessed February 2021. <https://www.genome.gov/Funded-Programs-Projects/ELSI-Research-Program-ethical-legal-social-implications>

³ National Science Foundation, “Broader Impacts Review Criterion”. Accessed February 2021.

<https://www.nsf.gov/pubs/2007/nsf07046/nsf07046.jsp>

⁴ CEN Workshop SATORI – Ethics assessment of research and innovation (Part 1: Ethics assessment unit, Aug. 2016 and Part 2: Ethical impact assessment framework, July 2016), European Committee for Standardization.

<https://www.cen.eu/news/workshops/Pages/WS-2016-010.aspx>

⁵ Barnard-Wills, David, Kush Wadhwa and David Wright, *Toolkit for Societal Impact Assessment in Security Research, Report on Deliverable 3.2*, ASSERT project, 2014. <http://assert-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2013/04/ASSERT-D3.2.pdf>.

⁶ Brey, Philip, et al, *D6.1: Generalised methodology for ethical assessment of emerging technologies*, SIENNA project, 2021 forthcoming.

Inputs from SIENNA WP2 (on genomics), WP3 (on human enhancement), and WP4 (on AI and robotics) informed our definition of ‘societal concerns’ and fed into the list of societal concerns included in the Annex. Specific deliverables consulted included:

- **SIENNA D2.4, D3.4, and D4.4:** Ethical Analysis of human genetics and genomics⁷; human enhancement technologies⁸, and AI and robotics technologies⁹;
- **SIENNA D2.5, D3.5, and D4.5** (public opinion surveys): Public views on genetics, genomics and gene editing¹⁰, human enhancement technologies¹¹, and artificial intelligence and robots¹²; and
- **SIENNA D2.6, D3.6, and D4.6** (citizen panels): Qualitative research exploring public attitudes to human genomics¹³, human enhancement technologies¹⁴, and AI and robotics.¹⁵

Consultation with PRFOs took place primarily in two identical workshops, hosted online and facilitated by Trilateral Research on December 8 and 9, 2020. Invitations were sent to 35 organisations (including one network of funding organisations). Representatives from the Austrian Research Promotion Agency, European Commission, Health Research Board (Ireland), Latvian Science Council, Research Council of Norway, and VINNOVA (Sweden) participated in the workshops; there were seven women and one man. After Trilateral Research presented briefly on the SIENNA project and societal concerns, participants shared information about current policies and procedures related to addressing societal concerns at their respective organisations. Participants discussed specific pilot programmes and ideas¹⁶ on how to overcome challenges related to addressing societal concerns, many of which appear

⁷ Alexandra Soulier, Emilia Niemiec, & Heidi Carmen Howard, *SIENNA D2.4: Ethical Analysis of Human Genetics and Genomics (Version V0.3)*, SIENNA project, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4068016>

⁸ Sean R. Jensen, *SIENNA D3.4: Ethical Analysis of Human Enhancement Technologies (Version V1.1)*, SIENNA project, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4068071>

⁹ Philip Jansen, Philip Brey, Alice Fox, Jonne Maas, Bradley Hillas, Nils Wagner, ... David Douglas. *SIENNA D4.4: Ethical Analysis of AI and Robotics Technologies (Version V1.1)*, SIENNA project, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4068083>

¹⁰ Tim Hanson, *SIENNA D2.5: Public views on genetics, genomics and gene editing in 11 EU and non-EU countries (Version V4)*, SIENNA project, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4081155>

¹¹ Marie Prudhomme, *SIENNA D3.5: Public views of human enhancement technologies in 11 EU and non-EU countries (Version V4)*, SIENNA project, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4068194>

¹² Rebecca Hamlyn, *SIENNA D4.5 Public views on artificial intelligence and robots across 11 EU and non-EU countries*, SIENNA project, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4068220>

¹³ Kantar (Public Division), *SIENNA D2.6: Qualitative research exploring public attitudes to human genomics (Version V3)*, SIENNA project, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4081178>

¹⁴ Kantar (Public Division), *SIENNA D3.6: Qualitative research exploring public attitudes to human enhancement technologies (Version V3)*, SIENNA project, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4081193>

¹⁵ Kantar (Public Division), *SIENNA D4.6: Qualitative research exploring public attitudes to AI and robotics (Version V3)*, SIENNA project, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4081247>

¹⁶ See, e.g., The CIMULACT (Citizen and Multi-Actor Consultation on Horizon 2020) project, funded by the European Commission under Grant Agreement number 665948, 2015-18. <http://www.cimulact.eu> (example of project funded by a PRFO to solicit public feedback in the process of setting research priorities); Digital Life Norway, The Research Council of Norway. <https://www.digitallifenorway.org> (example of PRFO creating research center supporting multi- and transdisciplinary research projects and skills); Fast Track Digital, The Austrian Research Promotion Agency (FFG). <https://www.ffg.at/en/programme/fast-track-digital> (example of PRFO creating research work programme specifically requiring interdisciplinary research consortia); Health Research Board Ireland, “Public reviews now integrated into HRB funding decisions”, 29 June 2020.

in the PRFO methodology as potential ways to implement the recommendations. Additionally, individual interviews were conducted with PRFO representatives from the National Science Foundation (Poland), National Centre for Research and Development (Poland), and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council. In mid-January, workshop participants were sent the draft methodology and invited to provide feedback; four expert representatives from PRFOs provided written comments.¹⁷

3. Researchers' needs and societal concerns

3.1 Researchers' needs

In addition to funding and resources to carry out research, researchers need clarity, flexibility, and support from research funders. While this report is not focused specifically on researcher's needs, a short reflection is relevant to thinking about how PRFOs can help researchers identify and address societal concerns in their research activities. These needs have been taken into consideration in the drafting of the PRFO methodology.

Clarity: Researchers need to know what is expected of them, both in the proposal writing process and in carrying out research. Therefore, PRFOs should clearly and publicly communicate policies and expectations that researchers will be expected to follow. This is especially true when new expectations, such as those related to societal concerns, are introduced.

Flexibility: Researchers need to be able to adapt research activities to foreseen and unforeseen challenges. PRFOs should allow researchers to amend research plans, within reason, to investigate new research directions and change research design, especially to implement appropriate interventions that minimise potential negative impacts and harms related to societal concerns.

Support: Researchers need resources and guidance to carry-out research activities, particularly those unrelated to their immediate field of expertise or research experience (e.g. identifying societal concerns). Approaches like stakeholder engagement and cross-disciplinary research require new sets of skills that not all researchers will have. PRFOs should commit to helping researchers by making resources and guidance readily available.

<https://www.hrb.ie/news/news-story/article/public-reviews-now-integrated-into-hrb-funding-decisions/> (example of PRFO directly engaging members of the public in proposal review process); and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council, Centres for Doctoral Training. <https://epsrc.ukri.org/skills/students/centres/> (example of PRFO creating studentship program encouraging multi-disciplinary research and offering training to researchers, including on responsible innovation).

¹⁷ Particular thanks to Anne Cody, Health Research Board Ireland; Anila Nauri and Helge Rynning, The Research Council of Norway; and Ben Rendell, UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council for their feedback and comments.

3.2 Societal concerns

For the purpose of this method, we define ‘societal concerns’ as issues (1) identified by the general public, (2) related to negative impacts or harms, (3) that result – directly or indirectly – from research activities and outputs involving emerging technologies. Each element of this definition is discussed below.

(1) Identified by the general public: This methodology is specifically focused on the concerns raised by the non-expert members of the general public, as opposed to the concerns of experts, policy makers, and industry representatives. The general public refers to both society-at-large and groups of individuals. Therefore, this methodology relies on a bottom-up approach to identifying societal concerns.

(2) Related to negative impacts or harms. While we recognise that research produces and leads to countless positive impacts on society, this methodology is focused on the negative impacts and harms. Societal concerns may be actual (i.e. already causing harm), potential (i.e. risk of harm), or perceived (i.e. erroneously believed to cause harm).

(3) Result – directly or indirectly – from research outputs involving emerging technologies. This methodology is concerned with the impacts of research outside of the immediate research context, which is distinct from research ethics that are concerned with the conduct of researchers during the research process (i.e. research integrity). Research outputs refers to knowledge (general and applied), artifacts (e.g. products, services, and platforms), and data produced or generated during the research lifecycle. Impacts may be intentional or unintentional, and anticipated or unanticipated. Impacts also relates to accident, malfunction, misuse, or abuse of research outputs.

The focus on societal concerns in this report is meant to complement identification of the concerns of experts, policy makers, and industry. It is true that the concerns of researchers, for example, may be identical or very similar to concerns from non-expert members of the public; researchers are, after all, also members of the general public. However, the objective of this methodology is to capture the concerns of the public that might otherwise be missed. PRFOs and researchers should actively look for ways to identify concerns of all stakeholders.

There is no exhaustive list of societal concerns. Types and categories of societal concerns will evolve and change over time as negative impacts emerge and are better understood. Additionally, relevant societal concerns differ depending on the type of research and anticipated outcomes. The societal concerns identified in the SIENNA project, which can serve as an initial list of ethical, human rights, and socio-economic concerns, are presented in the Annex.

4. SIENNA methodology to identify and address societal concerns

This methodology is divided into three steps: (1) identify and define, (2) understand, and (3) address. Each step includes recommendations for PRFOs, as well as specific ideas to implement the recommendation. While this methodology is described here in three sequential steps, in practice it is unlikely that each step will be clearly defined. The process of identifying and addressing societal concerns should be continuous and flexible. The steps will overlap, and there may be a need to revisit previous steps as new information emerges. Additionally, the process should not end after one cycle of review. Instead, there should be periodic reassessments to ensure that relevant concerns have been identified and are appropriately addressed.

This methodology draws on existing frameworks and risk assessment methodologies related to addressing societal concerns, such as Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)¹⁸; Ethical, legal and social implications/aspects (ELSI/ELSA) approach¹⁹; Broader Impact criteria²⁰; and social, ethical, environmental and socio-economic impact assessments.²¹ However, this methodology is intended to more comprehensively capture broader societal concerns about impacts of new and emerging technologies, and specifically provide guidance to PRFOs.

Step 1: Identify and define relevant societal concerns.

The first step is discovering the concerns of the general public in relation to emerging technologies. Relevant societal concerns differ depending on the type of research and anticipated outcomes, and the concerns evolve over time as technologies develop, and medium and long-term impacts are better known and understood. Societal concerns may be actual (i.e. already causing harm), potential (i.e. risk of harm), or perceived (i.e. erroneously believed to cause harm). Therefore, periodic assessment to identify and define societal concerns is necessary to ensure that relevant concerns are appropriately defined.

Recommendation 1.1: Adopt high-level policy recognising the need to identify and address societal concerns related to research on new and emerging technologies.

High-level policies help define objectives, communicate priorities and expectations, and provide a framework for consistency in decision-making. Adopting a high-level policy recognising the importance of addressing societal concerns is a clear sign to members of the public that their voices are heard.

¹⁸ European Commission, “Responsible Research and Innovation”. Accessed February 2021.

¹⁹ National Human Genome Research Institute, “Ethical, Legal and Social Implications Research Program. Accessed February 2021.

²⁰ National Science Foundation, Broader Impacts Review Criterion. Access February 2021.

²¹ See, e.g., CEN Workshop SATORI – Ethics assessment of research and innovation (Part 1: Ethics assessment unit, Aug. 2016 and Part 2: Ethical impact assessment framework, July 2016), European Committee for Standardization and Barnard-Wills, David, Kush Wadhwa and David Wright, *Toolkit for Societal Impact Assessment in Security Research, Report on Deliverable 3.2*, 2014.

As a first step, **PRFOs should develop and communicate how societal concerns will be defined**, based on the baseline definition presented in this method. Instead of aiming for a strict and exhaustive definition, PRFOs should focus on identifying the key characteristics and types of impacts relevant to their specific research areas. Once articulated, the definition can be used in planning funding priorities, when requiring researchers to indicate impacts, and in monitoring and evaluating projects. **Addressing societal concerns through risk mitigation and harm reduction must be central to the policy.** It is not enough to identify societal concerns; there must be a commitment to actively address concerns and minimise harms related to research in new and emerging technologies. A PRFO's **commitment should include both actions taken internally, as well as expectations and requirements for researchers.** Many suggested actions to address societal concerns are discussed in this methodology.

As part of developing a policy to address societal concerns, **PRFOs should engage with members of the public** (i.e. not experts, policymakers, or industry representatives) for input and feedback, for example through a public consultation or working group with civil society organisations. **PRFOs should also consult with experts from diverse disciplines**, particularly ethics, human rights, and social sciences and humanities.

Recommendation 1.2: Maintain an illustrative list of societal concerns and update as necessary.

To complement a policy to address societal concerns, PRFOs should create a list of societal concerns to guide internal decision-making and researchers' activities. With a list to consult as reference, PRFOs can better assess proposals, monitor projects, and evaluate research trends, and researchers will have more clarity on what is expected of them. The list could be compiled in consultation with members of the public and researchers. Societal concerns identified in research proposals, for example, could be the basis of an initial list. The list should be a dynamic, non-exhaustive, working document, as types and categories of societal concerns will evolve and change over time as negative impacts emerge and are better understood. To ensure that the list remains current, **PRFOs should develop a process for periodic reassessment of the identified societal concerns.**

Societal concerns, by definition, must come from the general public. As such, **PRFOs should engage with members of the public** to develop this list, for example through *ad hoc* working groups or permanent advisory committees. Here again, **PRFOs should also consult with experts from diverse disciplines**, particularly ethics, human rights, and social sciences and humanities. While there is no definitive, exhaustive list of societal concerns, **findings from the SIENNA Project can serve as a baseline.** PRFOs could specifically encourage and **fund research projects to identify and understand societal concerns**, with the explicit expectation that the findings would be used by the PRFO in future planning.

Step 2: Understand how research creates impact.

The second step is to understand how research relating to new and emerging technologies creates negative impacts and harms. This should include understanding of both anticipated and actual impacts, and in some cases may also involve perceived harms that never materialise. Impacts can be identified by the PRFOs, the researchers themselves, or members of the public.

Questions to ask when evaluating whether there are negative impacts or harms related to research in new and emerging technologies include:

- Are there negative societal impacts associated with the intended use or application of the research?

- Are human rights violated or negatively impacted by the research?
- Are ethical values and principles undermined by the research?
- Is the research vulnerable to misuse?
- Does the research have a disproportionately negative effect on specific groups, particularly vulnerable or traditionally unrepresented groups?

Recommendation 2.1: Conduct stakeholder engagement to understand how societal concerns are connected to research.

Recommendations 1.2 and 2.1 go hand in hand; members of the public should play an active role in both identifying societal concerns and explaining how those concerns are connected to research activities. Members of the public may represent themselves directly as individuals or through groups, for example civil society organisations. Where possible, **PRFOs should conduct stakeholder engagement activities with members of the public as part of strategic planning and when setting research funding priorities.** Members of the public have opinions about impacts of research, both negative and positive, because they often experience the impacts first-hand (e.g., patients in health research who directly benefit from new health technologies). Therefore, stakeholder engagement with members of the public is a critical part of understanding how research can result in harms.

‘Stakeholder’ refers to relevant actors (person, group or organisation) who: (1) might be affected by a research project; (2) have the potential to implement a research project’s results and findings; (3) have a stated interest in the research project fields; and/or, (4) have the knowledge and expertise to propose strategies and solutions.²² For research projects involving new and emerging technologies, stakeholder groups include scientists, ethicists, research ethics committees, professional organisations, civil society organisations, industry, policy makers, and the general public.

‘Stakeholder engagement’ is “an iterative process of actively soliciting the knowledge, experience, judgment and values of individuals selected to represent a broad range of direct interests in a particular issue.”²³ The purpose of stakeholder engagement in the context of research is to access diverse knowledge and skills,²⁴ make “relevant, transparent and effective decisions”,²⁵ and increase influence and impact.²⁶ There are many types of stakeholder engagement activities, including: interviews, focus groups, consultations, webinars, panels, questionnaires/surveys, workshops, dialogue events, and conferences.

²² Rowena Rodrigues, Stearns Broadhead, Philip Brey, Zuzanna Warso, Tim Hanson, Lisa Tambornino, & Dirk Lanzerath, *SIENNA D1.1: The consortium’s methodological handbook (Version V0.6)*, SIENNA project, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4247383>

²³ Deverka, et al., “Stakeholder participation in comparative effectiveness research: defining a framework for effective engagement”, *Journal of Comparative Effectiveness Research*, Vol. 1, Issue 2, 2012, pp. 181–94.

²⁴ Boaz et al., “How to engage stakeholders in research: design principles to support improvement”, *Health Research Policy and Systems*, Vol. 16, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12961-018-0337-6> (discussing the SEE-Impact study).

²⁵ Deverka, et al., “Stakeholder participation in comparative effectiveness research: defining a framework for effective engagement”, 2012.

²⁶ Boaz et al., “How to engage stakeholders in research: design principles to support improvement”, *Health Research Policy and Systems*, 2018.

In all stakeholder engagement activities, there is a need to ensure diversity in stakeholder representation (e.g., gender, ethnicity, ability, sexual orientation). In particular, minorities and other disadvantaged members of society must be included, as they are often the ones who experience the greatest negative impacts of technologies, while at the same time being those whose voices are the least heard.

However, there are many challenges to stakeholder engagement, and more research is needed to better understand how to appropriately and effectively involve members of the public. This is true of stakeholder engagement undertaken by PRFOs and research consortia. Particularly challenges include identifying members of the public who are willing and able to make meaningful contributions, and identifying representatives with the authority to speak on behalf of the public. Furthermore, stakeholder engagement activities are extremely time and resource consuming. **PRFOs can fund specific research into better understanding how to conduct stakeholder engagement in more effective, inclusive, and cost-efficient ways**, or provide infrastructure funding to support involvement of the public, with a particular focus on strategies to involve the public in identifying and addressing societal concerns.

Recommendation 2.2: Evaluate societal impacts of previously funded research.

In addition to learning what the public experiences (or perceives) to be societal concerns related to research, PRFOs should conduct internal analysis on how research activities relate to societal concerns. Therefore, **PRFOs should assess the impacts of previously funded research**. This should include, to the extent possible, identification of short, medium, and long-term impacts. By building a taxonomy of research activities and impacts, PRFOs can recognise trends and linkages that should inform future funding decisions.

Step 3: Address societal concerns and mitigate harms.

The third, and arguably most, important step is to take action to address societal concerns and minimise negative impacts. Societal concerns should be addressed as early as possible in the research process, and in practical ways that maximise the beneficial aspects of research while protecting society to the highest degree possible from negative impacts and harm. At the policy planning phase, PRFOs might align funding priorities and programmes to ensure investments are made into research in new and emerging technologies that do not have significant negative impacts on society. At the proposal stage, PRFOs should require researchers to make commitments to avoid or minimise negative impacts on society, identify foreseeable societal concerns, and create research proposals with the appropriate resources to address concerns as they arise throughout the research process. Additionally, at the proposal stage, PRFOs can make innovative changes to the proposal review process to ensure that foreseeable harms are mitigated as early as possible, before the research even begins. Lastly, throughout a research project, PRFOs and researchers should work together to continuously monitor for negative impacts (both anticipated and unanticipated) and implement mitigation interventions to avoid or minimise harms related to societal concerns.

Recommendation 3.1: Align funding priorities and programmes with societal concerns.

For PRFOs that have authority to direct or influence funding priorities, societal concerns should be a key consideration. Funding programmes should be designed in a way that recognises the significance of societal concerns and minimises negative impacts. A common approach and shared commitment across internal programmes and research divisions would increase consistency, facilitate resource sharing, and improve likelihood that societal concerns are appropriately addressed.

Ways that PRFOs can align funding priorities and programmes with societal concerns:

- **Involve the public in setting research priorities.** Public research funding comes from the public and “research is carried out in the name of society as an expression and reflection of the society’s needs, interests, priorities and expected impacts.”²⁷ Therefore, the public should be involved in defining and developing public research agendas related to new and emerging technologies. Similar approaches are already being tested in health research, where patients and patient groups are consulted on health-related research plans.²⁸ This could be done through a number of different avenues, including multi-stakeholder consultation, focus groups, and committees – all of which would involve individuals and/or representative from civil society organisations. The public could be asked to suggest potential research topics, consulted on proposed research programmes, or invited to help draft call text.
- **Create innovative funding initiatives.** PRFOs could design specific funding initiatives as an alternative to traditional funding models. For example, instead of pre-selecting research topics and inviting proposals that address the call text, PRFOs could invite researchers to define their own research challenge. PRFOs could also explore partial funding models, where research would be co-funded with other institutions such as charities or civil society organisations. Innovative models create a space for more creativity from researchers and may better address societal concerns (though detailed evaluation would be necessary to ensure that harms are at least on par with more established funding mechanisms)
- **Consult experts from ethics, human rights and social sciences and humanities.** Non-scientific experts can provide research-based insight on the impacts of new and emerging technologies and help PRFOs design priorities and programmes that address societal concerns.

Recommendation 3.2: Require greater ethical and social responsibility commitments from researchers to avoid or minimise negative impacts on society.

Often, research ethics focuses on responsible conduct of research and research integrity (i.e. microethics), which emphasises data management, research misconduct, treatment of research subjects, authorship concerns, publication practices, and conflicts of interest. While extremely valuable, this focus alone is not sufficient to adequately address societal concerns. This is especially true for research in new and emerging technologies, where potential societal impacts are global and result in substantial changes to the way society functions.

While experts in other fields have obligations to act in the interest of members of society – doctors have the Hippocratic oath, and engineers have the Paramountcy principle to ensure the safety, health and welfare of the public²⁹ – there is not yet a similar universal obligation for researchers working in new and emerging technologies. However, there is growing interest in the ‘social responsibility’ of

²⁷ Stephanie J. Bird, “Social Responsibility and Research Ethics: Not Either/Or but Both”, American Association for the Advancement of Science, 3 July 2014. <https://www.aaas.org/news/social-responsibility-and-research-ethics-not-eitheror-both>

²⁸ See, e.g., Oudendammer et al., “Patient participation in research funding: an overview of when, why and how amongst Dutch health funds”, *Research Involvement and Engagement*, Vol. 5, Issue 22, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40900-019-0163-1>

²⁹ National Society of Professional Engineer, Code of Ethics for Engineers. <https://www.nspe.org/resources/ethics/code-ethics>

researchers to “attend to the foreseeable societal impacts of their work, particularly as these impacts affect the safety, health or welfare of the society”³⁰ and make “meaningful contribution to the safeguarding or promoting of a peaceful, just and sustainable world society”.³¹ Others call for ethical principles from biomedical ethics³² to be applied to research in new and emerging technologies, namely the principles of beneficence (act for the benefit of others) and non-maleficence (avoid harm on others).³³ PRFOs can play a major role in putting ethics and social responsibility at the forefront of research on new and emerging technologies by **asking researchers to respect the principles of social responsibility, beneficence, and non-maleficence.**

Recommendation 3.3: Encourage researchers to identify potential negative impacts related to societal concerns early in the research process.

Most PRFOs require funding applicants to provide an impact summary explaining the scientific, technical and/or economic significance of proposed research as part of the funding application. With a desire to secure funding, researchers understandably focus on the positive, highlighting contributions to innovation and efficiency within the context of specific fields of research.

While these impact assessments are valuable, they are not sufficient to address societal concerns. Researchers are part of society and their research shapes society. Researchers – and those funding research – should understand how research will impact society at large. This process should begin at the proposal stage and should continue throughout the lifecycle of a research project. While researchers cannot be expected to foresee all potential impacts and harms, researchers should have an obligation to identify reasonably anticipated negative impacts as early as possible. Increasingly, calls for frameworks like ‘Ethical AI’ demonstrative collective momentum toward better understanding the broader impacts of new and emerging technologies.

Ways that PRFOs can encourage or require researchers to identify potential negative impacts related to societal concerns:

- **Broaden the scope of impact summaries in proposals.** In addition to scientific, technical and economic impacts, PRFOs could ask researchers to identify socio-economic and human rights-related impacts. Researchers might be asked to indicate how impact differs at the local, domestic, regional, or international level, which requires consideration of how communities are affected differently. PRFOs could also encourage or require researchers to explain the consequences of anticipated risks, such as accident, malfunction, misuse, or abuse of research outputs. In some cases, PRFOs could require researchers to explicitly address potential impacts relative to specific societal goals or challenges (e.g. Sustainable Development Goals).
- **Encourage researchers to conduct future-oriented analysis** as a means to understand the impacts (particularly long-term impacts) of research. Futures and foresight analysis refers to a

³⁰ Stephanie J. Bird, “Social Responsibility and Research Ethics: Not Either/Or but Both”, 3 July 2014.

³¹ Zandvoort, et al., “Editors’ Overview: Perspectives on Teaching Social Responsibility to Students in Science and Engineering”, *Science and Engineering Ethics*, Vol. 19, Issue 4, December 2013, p. 1414.

³² E.g., Beauchamp, T. L. and Childress, J. F, *Principles of Biomedical Ethics*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2012.

³³ These conversations are particularly prominent in the field of artificial intelligence. See Floridi, Luciano and Josh Cowls, “A Unified Framework of Five Principles for AI in Society”, *Harvard Data Science Review*, Vol. 1(1), 2 July 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1162/99608f92.8cd550d1>

range of method and tools, including forecasting and scenario development. The underlying premise of futures and foresight analysis is that the future is not predetermined; while we can reflect on future scenarios, the future is influenced by choices in the present.³⁴ Encouraging researchers to engage in future and foresight analysis requires both structured identification of societal concerns and thoughtful review of the ways that those risks and harms can be prevented or mitigated. Researchers should be encouraged to involve expertise from ethics, human rights, and social sciences when assessing potential impacts at the proposal stage (as well as throughout the project).

Recommendation 3.4: Encourage cross-disciplinary, multi-stakeholder research consortia.

No single researcher or discipline has the knowledge and tools to effectively carry out research involving complex societal challenges, particularly those that involve new and emerging technologies. Nor can a single researcher simultaneously be expected to be an ethicist, legal expert, and economist. Research consortia, therefore, should consist of experts from disciplines and non-expert stakeholders, each of which bring complementary sets of knowledge to a project.

Cross-disciplinary research – characterised as multi-, inter-, or trans-disciplinary – refers to research that involves experts from two or more disciplines. This collaborative approach is “key element in the advancement of science,” as it is “associated with high level of creativity, progress, and innovation.”³⁵ Cross-disciplinary expertise is especially important when it is difficult to adequately capture societal concerns through direct engagement with members of the public. While not a replacement for direct engagement, experts from ethics, human rights, and social sciences and humanities can help research teams identify potential concerns that would be raised by the public. A multi-stakeholder approach refers to the active and continuous participation of non-academics in research consortia as project partners (e.g. civil society organisations). Both approaches, which can be implemented simultaneously, encourage research teams to go beyond disciplinary silos and collaborate to identify and address societal concerns.

Ways that PRFOs can encourage or require that research consortia include partners with cross-disciplinary and multi-stakeholder representation include:

- **Incorporate cross-disciplinarity and multi-stakeholder representation as factors in the proposal assessment criteria**, as either an explicit requirement or positive consideration. PRFOs could specifically call for particular types of representation, for example experts from social science and humanities (SSH) or civil society organisations.
- **Dedicate funding to support cross-disciplinary, multi-stakeholder research activities.** Non-traditional research activities may take longer and require more resources than traditional scientific research. They also require different structural administrative mechanisms to manage more complex project activities. By explicitly allowing funding for such activities,

³⁴ Joseph Voros, “A Primer on Futures Studies: Foresight and the Use of Scenarios”, *prospect*, No. 6, Dec. 2001. <https://static1.squarespace.com/static/580c492820099e7e75b9c3b4/t/58abbe7c29687fbaf4a03324/1487650430788/A+Primer+on+Futures+Studies.pdf>

³⁵ Bourdons et al., “Analysis of Cross-Disciplinary Research Through Bibliometric Tool”, *Handbook of Quantitative Science and Technology Research*, 2004, pp. 437-456. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/1-4020-2755-9_20

PRFOs directly support researchers in developing and implementing a cross-disciplinary, multi-stakeholder approach.

- **Create guidance, tools, and resources to help researchers develop and implement a cross-disciplinary, multi-stakeholder approach.** There is increasing recognition of the value of cross-disciplinary, multi-stakeholder approaches to research, but little practical guidance tailored to research specifically on new and emerging technologies. PRFOs could play a role, in collaboration with researchers, to create guidance materials and tools (e.g., training) specific to the challenges associated with this field of research, with particular attention on the ways that a cross-disciplinary, multi-stakeholder approach can help PRFOs and researchers better address societal concerns.
- **Facilitate learning and exchange of best practices amongst projects.** PRFOs can encourage researchers to reflect on their own experiences addressing societal concerns and share lessons learned with other researchers by, for example, clustering related projects, creating research networks, or establishing centralised repositories/centres of expertise.

Recommendation 3.5: Encourage and fund activities involving stakeholder engagement with members of the public.

Just as PRFOs should engage with the public to identify and understand societal concerns [see Recommendation 2.1], **PRFOs can encourage or require researchers to carry out stakeholder engagement with the general public** as a means to identify and address societal concerns that may arise from research activities. Stakeholder engagement entails active participation of stakeholders, unlike ‘research participation’ where research ‘subjects’ take “part in a research study as a means of generating specific data as determined by researchers.”³⁶

Members of the public could be formally brought into research projects, for example as members of advisory boards or councils, or invited to participate through surveys or consultations. These individuals or representatives from civil society organisations could be kept informed about research plans and progress and invited to comment on potential concerns. Going a step further, they could also be involved in creating mitigation strategies and/or asked to provide feedback on options developed by the research team. **PRFOs can support researchers by developing guidance, tools, and training on how to use stakeholder engagement to help identify and address societal concerns.**

However, as discussed in Recommendation 2.1, there are many challenges to stakeholder engagement, and more research is needed to better understand how to appropriately and effectively involve members of the public.

Recommendation 3.6: Modify proposal review process to optimise assessment of societal impacts.

Traditionally, competitive scientific research grants are awarded through a process of peer review by a panel of experts, considered by some as “the gold standard” for reviewing research proposals. Yet despite its wide acceptance and prominent use for decades, there are increasing concerns that peer

³⁶ Boaz et al., “How to engage stakeholders in research: design principles to support improvement”, *Health Research Policy and Systems*, 2018.

review is not an appropriate method for selecting the best proposals,³⁷ including questions about its ability to adequately identify and address societal concerns in research proposals.

Peer review is conducted by panels of scientific experts, selected based on their research and experience in a given area of expertise. Historically the primary factor in deciding which proposals receive funding is the assessment of scientific merit (or excellence), not societal impact. Additionally, peer review tends to place heavy emphasis on past research success, particularly on publications and journal prestige. Therefore, researchers with multi-disciplinary experience and non-academics are less likely to receive funding, despite the quality of a proposal.

Ways that PRFOs can modify the proposal review process to optimise assessment of societal impacts include:

- **Diversify review panels to include cross-disciplinary representation.** Just as no single researcher or discipline has the knowledge and tools to effectively carry out research involving complex societal challenges [see Recommendation 3.4], a panel of experts from the same discipline (or even closely related disciplines) do not have the knowledge to adequately assess societal concerns in a research proposal. Proposals should be reviewed by panels with representation from ethics, human rights, and social sciences and humanities perspectives. Panels should also have diversity in terms of gender and representation from vulnerable and minority groups.
- **Include non-experts and members of the public.** Multi-stakeholder representation brings “a wider range of knowledge and experience [that] improves transparency, limits the danger of bias and contributes to addressing social benefits.”³⁸ There are many ways PRFOs could involve non-experts and members of the public. For example, individuals or representatives from civil society organisations could sit on a review panel alongside experts or contribute an independent assessment for consideration, or the public at large could be invited to comment on proposals via an open public consultation.
- **Train reviewers to recognise societal concerns.** Reviewers – from all backgrounds – could be trained on the significance of addressing societal concerns and given resources to identify potential negative impacts and harms that could be anticipated at the proposal stage.
- **Require appropriate harm mitigation interventions when needed.** Incorporating some of the strategies discussed below in Recommendation 3.7, researchers should be required to avoid or minimise foreseeable negative impacts or harms apparent at the proposal stage. Reviewers could receive training on developing impact mitigation interventions, and researchers required to modify research proposals as necessary to appropriately address societal concerns.

Recommendation 3.7: Encourage and support impact monitoring and mitigation throughout research activities.

Identifying negative impacts related to research on emerging technologies and mitigating potential harm is crucial to effectively addressing societal concerns. Researchers need support – including

³⁷ Sandra Bendiscioli, “The troubles with peer review for allocating research funding: Funders need to experiment with versions of peer review and decision-makers”, *EMBO Reports*, Vol. 20, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.15252/embr.201949472>.

³⁸ Ibid.

guidance, funding, and tools – to monitor their research activities and develop impact mitigation strategies.

There are four key components of this recommendation. First, **monitoring for societal concerns is more comprehensive than traditional impact reporting**, which often focuses on immediate ‘positive’ impacts and contributions that researchers want to highlight, or on activities – meetings, papers, speeches – equated to impact.³⁹ Like requiring broader societal impact analysis at the proposal stage, monitoring for societal concerns requires a more robust, long-term approach to identifying potential impacts and harms that may result, directly or indirectly, from research activities and outputs. Impact monitoring should include consideration of the potential harms associated with accident, malfunction, misuse, or abuse of new technologies or the research data.

Second, it is not enough to identify and report on potential negative impacts. **Actions should be taken to avoid or minimise harm**, which includes appropriate interventions and modifications to research activities.

Third, both **monitoring and impact mitigation requires cross-disciplinary input from experts and stakeholders**. With representatives from different perspectives, research teams can identify a broader scope of societal concerns and generate more options for preventative measures, thus enhancing likelihood of developing an acceptable strategy. Cross-disciplinary research teams and stakeholder engagement is therefore, once again, essential.

Fourth, **monitoring and impact mitigation should be a continuous process, not just an end-of-project activity**. If red flags are identified through ongoing monitoring, time and resources can be designated for developing and implementing a mitigation strategy before risks are realised (or the project ends), thus increasing the likelihood that societal concerns are appropriately addressed.

The responsibility could be shared between researchers and PRFOs. PRFOs can encourage (or even require) that researchers undertake some activities and support researchers work through funding, guidance and tools. PRFOs can also conduct independent assessments to complement and guide research decisions and outcomes.

Ways that PRFOs can encourage and support impact monitoring and mitigation throughout research activities include:

- **Extend research funding to cover robust impact monitoring and mitigation activities undertaken by researchers.** Monitoring for broad societal harms takes significant time and resources. By explicitly allowing funding for such activities, PRFOs directly support researchers in carrying out these activities. In some cases, a set amount or percentage of funding could be specifically designated for risk monitoring and mitigation, thus implicitly requiring researchers to carry out develop and implement a plan for monitoring and addressing societal concerns.

³⁹ Duncan Green, “If academics are serious about research impact they need to learn from monitoring, evaluation and learning teams”, *LSE Impact Blog*, 11 July 2017.
<https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/impactofsocialsciences/2017/07/11/if-academics-are-serious-about-research-impact-they-need-to-learn-from-monitoring-evaluation-and-learning-teams/>

- **Develop key impact indicators.** While there would be some differences across specific technology research areas, PRFOs could develop (or commission the development) of key impact indicators related to societal concerns for all projects involving emerging technologies. Key indicators would help researchers better understand what to monitor and provide PRFOs with a quasi-standardised framework for overseeing monitoring. Key indicators should involve ethical, human rights, and socio-economic considerations, at a minimum. Key indicators should also be both descriptive and anticipatory, enabling identification of both actual negative impacts and ‘red flags.’ Societal concerns identified through existing research, including the SIENNA project, could be a starting point, but further research and analysis is needed.
- **Encourage researchers to conduct impact assessments and fund research into developing specific assessment methodologies for new and emerging technologies.** Impact assessment refers to a structured process of identifying intended and unintended impacts of a specific action or set of actions, with the intended objective of avoiding and/or mitigating negative impacts (and enhancing positive impacts) across the life cycle of the action.⁴⁰ Impact assessments take many forms, depending on the type of impact captured (e.g., ethical, environmental, human rights, socio-economic). Social impact assessments (SIA), developed in the 1970s in the context of large-scale environmental development projects, and now socio-economic impact assessments (SEIA), more specifically attempt to capture broader societal concerns. A key feature of social impact assessment is the participatory approach, meaning that diverse stakeholders should be engaged throughout the process.⁴¹ PRFOs could encourage, or even require, research projects to include an impact assessment that captures societal concerns. To support researchers, PRFOs should make funding available to conduct impact assessments as part of research activities; PRFOs could also develop tools, guidance or training to assist researchers in carrying out impact assessments. Furthermore, given that impact assessment methodologies for new and emerging technologies are rather nascent, PRFOs could specifically fund projects to further develop methods and tools specific to this research area, building on work in SIENNA on generalised methodology for SEIA of new and emerging technologies.
- **Develop guidance on impact mitigation strategies to address negative impacts and societal concerns.** Once a negative impact is identified, mitigation measures should be developed and implemented to avoid or minimise harm. In the current absence of specific frameworks for new and emerging technologies, PRFOs and researchers can draw from more established methodologies, such as environmental impact assessment and mitigation.⁴² The key focus of mitigation activities should be on preventative measures or measures that limit the severity, duration, and/or reach of harm. However, consideration is needed to ensure that the measures are also practical and feasible to integrate. Additionally, it is also important to distinguish between an obligation to hear concerns from the public, and an obligation to

⁴⁰ Esteves et al., “Social impact assessment: the state of the art”, *Impact Assessment and Project Appraisal*, Vol. 30, Issue 1, 2012, pp. 34-42. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14615517.2012.660356>

⁴¹ Vanclay, F., “International Principles for Social Impact Assessment”, *Impact Assessment and Project Appraisal*, Vol. 21, No. 1, March 2003, pp. 5-11. <https://doi.org/10.3152/147154603781766491>

⁴² International Institute for Sustainable Development, *The 7 Steps to an EIA – Step 3: Impact Assessment and Mitigation*, Accessed January 2021. <https://www.iisd.org/learning/eia/eia-7-steps/step-3-impact-assessment-and-mitigation/>

respond (i.e. develop a mitigation intervention). Not all concerns raised by the public will be valid or significant enough to merit a response. Part of the process of developing a mitigation strategy is determining which concerns and potential harms require responses, and to what degree the harm should be mitigated. As such, public feedback should be taken under consideration in addition to feedback from other stakeholder groups, including experts and policy-makers. PRFOs can support researchers by, for example, developing guidance documents, facilitating exchange of best practices amongst projects, or offering training.

- **Conduct independent impact assessments and develop mitigation strategies for research projects.** With dedicated resources, PRFOs (through project officers or other representatives) could independently monitor and assess research activities for societal concerns, either in place of or as a complement to the monitoring work done by research teams. Furthermore, PRFOs could develop mitigation interventions, and they could suggest, or require, that research teams implement certain actions. These types of activities would require dedicated resources from the PRFOs, as well a substantial knowledge by the project officer of the research activities.
- **Allow for greater flexibility in planned research activities to respond to unanticipated negative impacts related to societal concerns.** At times, harm mitigation may require significant deviation from planned research activities. Researchers need support from funders to appropriately adapt research activities, even if it means certain planned activities cannot be undertaken. PRFOs may consider whether, consistent with their own mandates and internal policies, it is possible to require significant modifications to research projects, or even halt research funding if the risk of societal harm is too great.

SIENNA methodology for public research funding organisations: Guide to identifying and addressing societal concerns in public research related to new and emerging technologies

Step 1: Identify and define relevant societal concerns.

- **Recommendation 1.1:** Adopt high-level policy recognising the need to identify and address societal concerns related to research on new and emerging technologies.
- **Recommendation 1.2:** Maintain an illustrative list of societal concerns and update as necessary.

Step 2: Understand how research creates impact.

- **Recommendation 2.1:** Conduct stakeholder engagement to understand how societal concerns are connected to research.
- **Recommendation 2.2:** Evaluate societal impacts of previously funded research.

Step 3: Address societal concerns and mitigate harms.

- **Recommendation 3.1:** Align funding priorities and programmes with societal concerns.
- **Recommendation 3.2:** Require greater ethical and social responsibility commitments from researchers to avoid or minimise negative impacts on society.
- **Recommendation 3.3:** Encourage researchers to identify potential negative impacts related to societal concerns early in the research process.
- **Recommendation 3.4:** Encourage cross-disciplinary, multi-stakeholder research consortia.
- **Recommendation 3.5:** Encourage and fund activities involving stakeholder engagement with members of the public.
- **Recommendation 3.6:** Modify proposal review process to optimise assessment of societal impacts.
- **Recommendation 3.7:** Encourage and support impact monitoring and mitigation throughout research activities.

5. Conclusion

Both PRFOs and researchers have an obligation to the public to ensure that research related to new and emerging technologies has a positive impact on society, which means that societal concerns must be identified and addressed in ways that avoids and mitigates harm. These recommendations are formulated to provide PRFOs with a practical method and range of tools, taking in account PRFOs' role in the research process and the needs of researchers for have clarity, flexibility, and support. These recommendations can be adapted and implemented, in part or in whole, to address societal concerns related to research involving new and emerging technologies.

Annex: Societal concerns identified in SIENNA

The following societal concerns were identified by the SIENNA project through desk research⁴³; and stakeholder engagement.⁴⁴ Stakeholder engagement activities included:

- Panels of citizens (five EU countries: France, Germany, Spain, Poland and Greece)⁴⁵ ;
- Public opinion surveys (seven EU and four non-EU countries: France, Germany, Greece, Netherlands, Poland, Spain, Sweden, Brazil, South Korea, South Africa, and United States)⁴⁶ ;
- Workshops with technology-specific experts, academics, policy-makers, and industry representatives; and
- Expert interviews.

These concerns related specifically to the three research areas of SIENNA: genomics, human enhancement, and AI and robotics. **This list is intended to serve as a baseline and be an example of societal concerns that research funding organisation, including PRFOs, and researchers should be aware of during their research activities.** This list is not an exhaustive list of societal concerns generally, nor should it be used as a definitive list of societal concerns related to the three research areas. PRFOs and researchers should engage in consultation with stakeholders and conduct impact assessments to identify additional societal concerns related to specific research activities.

Societal concerns related to genomics

- **Physical and psychological harms** from misinterpretation of genetic/genomic information (e.g. anxiety among people who receive probabilistic and uncertain results leading to lower quality of life).
- **New eugenics and decreased tolerance for diversity** (i.e. neo-eugenics, consumer eugenics, liberal eugenics, and libertarian eugenics): an ideology which advocates the use of reproductive technologies where the choice of “enhancing” human characteristics is left to the individual preferences of parents acting as consumers (e.g., ‘designer babies’), rather than the public health policies of the state. Particular concern for persons with disabilities.

⁴³ Alexandra Soulier, Emilia Niemiec, & Heidi Carmen Howard, *SIENNA D2.4: Ethical Analysis of Human Genetics and Genomics*, 2019; Sean R. Jensen, *SIENNA D3.4: Ethical Analysis of Human Enhancement Technologies (Version V1.1)*, 2020; and Philip Jansen, Philip Brey, Alice Fox, Jonne Maas, Bradley Hillas, Nils Wagner, ... David Douglas, *SIENNA D4.4: Ethical Analysis of AI and Robotics Technologies (Version V1.1)*, 2020.

⁴⁴ SIENNA Project, *Stakeholders, experts and citizens in SIENNA*. <https://www.sienna-project.eu/about-sienna/stakeholders/>

⁴⁵ Kantar (Public Division), *SIENNA D2.6: Qualitative research exploring public attitudes to human genomics (Version V3)*, 2019; Kantar (Public Division), *SIENNA D3.6: Qualitative research exploring public attitudes to human enhancement technologies (Version V3)*, 2019; and Kantar (Public Division), *SIENNA D4.6: Qualitative research exploring public attitudes to AI and robotics (Version V3)*, 2019.

⁴⁶ Tim Hanson, *SIENNA D2.5: Public views on genetics, genomics and gene editing in 11 EU and non-EU countries (Version V4)*, 2020; Marie Prudhomme, *SIENNA D3.5: Public views of human enhancement technologies in 11 EU and non-EU countries (Version V4)*, 2020; and Rebecca Hamlyn, *SIENNA D4.5 Public views on artificial intelligence and robots across 11 EU and non-EU countries*, 2020.

- **Genetic discrimination** and the rise of genetic underclasses where they would be stigmatised and discriminated in job, health insurance access and other social aspects of life. Particular concern for persons with disabilities.
- **Exacerbation of health disparities** between those with access to genomics technologies, research and therapies, and those without (instead of addressing social factors such as poverty and structural racism).
- **Inequality and discrimination**, especially if the genetic/genomic screening are made obligatory.
- **Privacy, confidentiality and security** of patient information, including concerns about what purpose and who accesses genomic data, and concerns of hacking and stealing information.
- **Prohibitive high costs**, leading to decreased access to therapeutics and endangering lives.
- **Genetic surveillance**, for example through forensic DNA profiling and databasing.
- **Medicalisation**, where non-medical aspects of human life come to be considered as medical ‘problems’.
- **Geneticisation**, where differences between individuals are reduced to their DNA
- **“Playing God” and questioning the nature of humanity.**
- Creating offspring of **“mutants and monsters”** via germline gene editing.
- **Use of embryos and germline gene editing.**
- **Lack of informed consent**, particularly with children (e.g., prenatal screening for DNA sequencing).
- **Unforeseeable future negative medical and social implications**, for example when parents give consent for genomic data or genetic manipulation can affect their offspring.
- **Intrusive long-term monitoring**, particularly of persons who undergo somatic gene editing (who may need to be monitored whole their lives).

Societal concerns related to human enhancement (HET)

- **Physical harms**, especially unanticipated side effects and long-term effects (e.g., related to putting hazardous chemicals or cheap/unsafe materials that could be harmful). In most instances the applications have either been recently developed or are currently being developed, and that as such it is impossible to know their full impact and all of the possible risks associated with them.
- **Psychological harms** creating negative impact on mental health, for example dependencies on/addictions to HET technologies; leading people on a never-ending search for perfection (if benefits only short-term); and reliance on technology for their well-being and sense of self-worth.
- **Greater inequality and increased discrimination**, for example unfair advantages related to access and adoption of HET, and individuals who refuse to use technology or cannot afford to use it will be discriminated against.
- **Unequal access** related to costs, potentially giving already powerful individuals increased means of control over peers.
- **Creation of a “superhuman” race**, when physical enhancement technology used to enhance the capabilities of human beings beyond what is deemed ‘normal’ especially in non-medical context and in the case of invasive technologies.
- **Changing nature of humanity and individual self-worth** if creating a world where the ‘self’ is lost and where individuality is controlled by technology (humans act or feel a certain way based on norms subjectively created by whoever will have the power to decide, e.g., how people

should feel, how they should perform, what they should look like, and how long they should live for).

- **Intolerance in society:** Fear for diversity and inclusion, and discrimination against anyone who is different – for instance people with physical disability if everyone is physically enhanced, or with mental health problems if everyone is emotionally enhanced. This in turn might put pressure on people to use technology to fit in with society, even if they might not have wished to do so.
- **Creation of ‘artificial’ and homogenous society** through suppressing differences, enforcing narrower perceptions of beauty, and creating a situation where everyone looks the same.
- **Creation of a “lazy society”**, where people would forget the meaning of effort and would not feel need to work.
- **Lack of informed consent** about short and long-term risks, especially in regard to children.
- Misused for **criminal activities**, for example doping and cheating.
- Use of **physical enhancement technology in the workplace, including risk of exploitation by employers.**
- **Use of physical enhancement technology in schools and with children.**

Societal concerns related to AI and robotics:

- **Loss of Freedom and Individual Autonomy**, which is related to how AI and robotics impact the ways people perceive they are in control of decisions, how they analyse the world, how they make decisions (e.g. impact of manipulative power of algorithms to nudge toward preferred behaviours), how they interact with one another, and how they modify their perception of themselves and their social and political environment.
- **Loss of human contact and dehumanisation of society** as AI and robotics replaces human connections, reducing the contact between people and causing isolation.
- **Unfairness and inequality concerning who owns, has access to, develops, and regulates AI technologies**, and how socio-economic impacts are addressed. Particularly concerning for minority and vulnerable groups, including women.
- **Potential for criminal and malicious use.**
- **Disappearance of jobs** and unemployment as robots replace human without sufficient alternative work options
- **Unsecure data and AI systems** vulnerable to attack, misuse, or manipulation.
- **Interference with democracy and political processes**, including rights to vote, protest peacefully, or form political opinion.
- **Physical harms**, for example the accidental killing of innocent civilians by drones/autonomous weapons.
- **Lack of Privacy and data protection**, including concerns related to intrusion in private life, unauthorized surveillance and illegal activities.
- **Lack of Transparency** about AI systems and related data, and the way decisions are taken that impact individuals, specially concerns about AI ‘black boxes’.
- **Harms to the environment** related to the entire lifecycle of AI, including high energy consumption, and impacts related to raw material extraction, manufacturing, storage, and disposal of AI-enabled devices.